

The Effects of Gaps in Ferrite Tiles on Both Absorber and Chamber Performance

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Abstract – In this paper, we present a model that accounts for the gaps between ferrite tiles which occur during the installation of the tiles in anechoic chambers. With this model we investigate the effect of gaps on both the performance of the tiles and the degradation of the chamber performance due to the gaps. It is shown that small gaps can cause large changes (as much as 5 to 10 dB) in the reflectivity, especially at the lower frequency end. It is also shown that small gaps can cause variations in chamber performance, and these variations can have a detrimental effect on the ability of the chamber to meet its performance specification.

INTRODUCTION

In the installation process of placing ferrite tiles on anechoic chamber walls, gaps between the individual tiles are inevitable. These gaps are depicted in Figure 1. It has been demonstrated in the past that these gaps have a detrimental effect on the overall performance of the ferrite tile absorber [1]-[3]. This is illustrated in Figure 2, where the measured reflectivity of a ferrite tile wall with gaps (3 mm gaps) and without gaps (gaps less than 0.1 mm) is depicted. The measurements in the figure were obtained from time-domain techniques [3]-[6].

The change in performance is due to the fact that the gaps that are present on a chamber wall change the equivalent or effective material properties of the ferrite absorber that the fields “see”. This degradation of the ferrite tile performance due to the gaps can have a substantial effect on the overall chamber performance. In fact, gaps as small as 0.3 mm can cause 1.5 dB changes in chamber performance.

In this paper, we present a model that accounts for those gaps. This model is developed from an analysis of a finite-difference time-domain (FDTD) model of the ferrite absorber with gaps. The model is used to investigate the variations of reflection coefficients of the ferrite tiles as a function of gap size. A FDTD

model, similar to that discussed in [7], is used to illustrate how the performance of a chamber degrades as a function of gap dimensions.

FDTD MODEL FOR THE REFLECTION COEFFICIENT FOR FERRITE TILE ABSORBER WITH GAPS

We use a FDTD model to calculate the reflectivity (the reflection coefficient in dB) for the wall of ferrite tiles with a uniform gap size g . In this FDTD model various gap sizes were subdivided into two spatial cells. For the cell sizes required to resolve the gaps (on the order of tenths of millimeters), the computational volume must be kept as small as possible so as not to exceed computer resources. This was accomplished by utilizing the periodicity of the ferrite gap tile structure (see Figure 1). Symmetric boundary conditions were applied in two spatial directions, allowing for two dimensions of the computational volume to be reduced to half a period of the structure (see Figure 3). A few wavelengths away from the air-ferrite interface a first-order Mur absorbing boundary condition was used [8].

In using a time domain analysis the issue that must be resolved is how to handle frequency dependence of materials in the time domain. The method we have chosen to handle the frequency dependence is similar to that discussed in [7]. By using the concept of magnetic susceptibility and a Debye model for the frequency dependence, the following FDTD scheme can be used.

The B field is given by

$$B = \mu H = \mu_0 H + M, \quad (1)$$

where

$$M = \mu_0 H \chi_m \quad (2)$$

and χ_m is the magnetic susceptibility; its frequency dependence is given by

$$\chi_m = \frac{K}{1 + j \frac{\omega}{2\pi f_o}}, \quad (3)$$

where K and f_o are constants representing the absorption peak and relaxation frequency of the bulk material. For the ferrite tiles used in this study these constants are $K = 1101.4$ and $f_o = 7.066 \cdot 10^6$. By replacing $j\omega$ with $\partial/\partial t$, we obtain a time-domain operator relating the current time value of M to the previous time values of M and B .

With this magnetic susceptibility approach, the time-marching scheme is implemented in the following manner.

1. Use the curl equation for E to obtain a finite-difference equation relating B to E . Calculate the current B fields from previous B and E fields.
2. Use equations (2) and (3) to obtain a difference equation relating M to B . Calculate the current M from the previous B and M .
3. Use $H^n = (B^n - M^n)/\mu$ to calculate the current H field.
4. Use the curl equation for H to calculate the current E field.

Figure 4 depicts the reflectivity for various gap dimensions for a ferrite tile backed by a dielectric layer and ground plane (see Figure 5a) obtained from this FDTD model. The ferrite tile has a width of 10 cm and a thickness of 6.5 mm, and the dielectric layer has a thickness of 13 mm and $\epsilon_r = 2$. Small changes in the gap dimension cause large changes in the reflectivity, especially at the lower frequency ranges. Similar behavior was demonstrated in [1] and [2].

This variation in reflectivity due to gaps ultimately results in variations in chamber performance and can cause a chamber to fail to meet a desired chamber performance specification. The issue that needs to be addressed is how large a change in chamber performance is caused by these small gap sizes. This is investigated by using a three-dimensional field computational model to predict the performance of two different anechoic chambers equipped with ferrite tile with various gap sizes.

EFFECTIVE LAYER MODEL OF FERRITE GAPS

This section presents a simple effective layer model that accurately predicts the reflection coefficient of a ferrite tile absorber with gaps. In previous work [7], we described how the finite-difference time-domain technique can be used to predict the performance of absorber-lined chambers for various testing scenarios. This allows for the validation of a particular absorber/chamber design prior to construction and allows for the retrofit of an existing shielded enclosure with new RF absorber material. Such a model can also be used to investigate the variation of chamber performance due to gaps in ferrite tiles.

Due to the typical gap size (on the order of 0.3 mm), we cannot spatially resolve the gaps in a full 3-dimensional chamber model. The small gaps would result in very large memory requirements and excessively large CPU run times. However, if the effects of the gaps can be modeled as a new effective material of the absorbing structure (replacing the ferrite tiles with gaps), then the effective material layer can be efficiently incorporated into full 3-dimensional chamber models.

The rationale for using an effective material property layer to represent the gap effect is as follows. The bulk material properties of a ferrite material can be represented by the following first-order Debye model

$$\mu_r = 1 + \frac{K}{1 + j \frac{f}{f_o}} \quad (4)$$

where once again the constants $K = 1101.4$ and $f_o = 7.066 \cdot 10^6$ represent the absorption peak and relaxation frequency of the bulk material. It is tempting to use the homogenization model presented in [9]-[11] to determine the effective material properties of the ferrite tile with gaps. Unfortunately, since the period (p in Figure 3) of the structure is large compared to the wavelength in the bulk ferrite, the homogenization model breaks down. However, homogenization does indicate that the gaps have the effect of shifting both the absorption peak and the relaxation frequency (K and f_o) of the effective ferrite tile gap structure. While the homogenization model is not adequate for determining the shift in K and f_o analytically, an optimization procedure can be used to accurately model the gap effects and hence determine the changes in K and f_o .

The ferrite tile with the gaps is replaced by an effective layer (see Figure 5b), and the material properties of the effective layer are obtained by a least-squares optimization method [6]. This procedure is described by the following. First, we assume that the material properties of this effective layer can be expressed in the following Debye representation

$$\mu_r = 1 + \frac{C_1}{1 + \frac{jf}{C_2}} + C_3 \quad (5)$$

where C_1 , C_2 , and C_3 are fitting constants. The additional fitting constant C_3 improves the fit. The reflectivity of the effective ferrite layer backed by a dielectric and a ground plane can be determined analytically with the three unknowns C_1 , C_2 , and C_3 . Second, the reflectivity of the ferrite tiles with gaps is determined with the 3-dimensional FDTD technique discussed above. The unknown constants can be determined by comparing this analytical solution to the numerical FDTD solution of the ferrite tiles with gaps and using a least-squares optimization procedure.

This method was implemented for a ferrite tile of width 10 cm, thickness of 6.5 mm for gap sizes of 0.2 mm, 0.3 mm, 0.4 mm, and 1.0 mm. The fitting constants from the least-squares optimization procedure for these various gap sizes are presented in Table 1. As the gap size increases, the absorption peak decreases and the relaxation frequency increases. With these constants determined, the reflectivity of the ferrite tile was calculated and the results are shown in Figure 6. This figure also shows the FDTD results. The optimized effective layer model shows good agreement with the FDTD results.

CHAMBER PERFORMANCE WITH GAPS

By replacing the ferrite tiles and gaps on the chamber walls with the effective layer model and using a 3-dimensional FDTD chamber model, it is possible to simulate the performance of a chamber with various gap sizes in the ferrite tiles to investigate the variations in the overall performance of the chamber. One benefit of this Debye effective layer model is that it is well suited for implementing frequency dependent material properties in time-domain codes (see [7]).

To use this effective layer model, the FDTD scheme described above needs to be modified to incorporate the three fitting constants (C_1 , C_2 , and C_3). With

these three constants the B field is now expressed as

$$B = \mu H = \mu_o (1 + C_3) H + M, \quad (6)$$

where

$$M = \mu_o H \chi_m \quad (7)$$

and χ_m is the magnetic susceptibility; its frequency dependence is given by

$$\chi_m = \frac{C_1}{1 + j \frac{\omega}{2\pi C_2}}, \quad (8)$$

where C_1 , C_2 , and C_3 are given in Table 1. With these new expressions for the B field and the susceptibility, a similar time-marching scheme to that above can be used.

The normalized site-attenuation for two differently sized chambers for various gap dimensions was calculated using this FDTD scheme along with the model presented in [7]. Figures 7 and 8 show the normalized site-attenuation and the deviation of the normalized site-attenuation from an ideal open area test site (OATS) for a 10-meter chamber of width 10.36 m (34 ft), length 21.34 m (70 ft), and height 8.23 m (27 ft). Figures 9 and 10 show the site-attenuation and deviation from an OATS for a 10-meter chamber of width 11.58 m (38 ft), length 19.81 m (65 ft), and height 8.02 m (26.3 ft). The results in both these figures correspond to vertical polarization. These results indicate that 1.5 dB variations in site-attenuation can be realized for gaps as small as 0.4 mm and much larger variation for 1 mm gaps. Since only ± 1 dB is budgeted for chamber imperfections ([9] and [12]), these variations can have a dramatic effect on the ability of the chamber to meet its specification. Thus, if a chamber is designed to just meet the ± 4 dB requirement and ferrite gaps are not taken into account, then it is possible that the designed chamber will fail the desired specification.

It should be noted that this analysis was performed for only one type of hybrid absorber. However, there is no indication that other types of hybrid absorbers will not have similar types of chamber performance degradations due to gaps in the ferrite tile. This point is presently being investigated.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, we investigated the effect of ferrite tile gaps on reflectivity performance, as well as gap effects on overall chamber performance. It was shown

Table 1: Fitting Constants for Gap Model.

Gap size	C_1	C_2	C_3
0.2 mm	735.5383	$9.894511 \cdot 10^6$	-0.860000
0.3 mm	514.7540	$13.98801 \cdot 10^6$	-0.860000
0.4 mm	400.0000	$17.98324 \cdot 10^6$	-0.958274
1.0 mm	203.0324	$35.02306 \cdot 10^6$	-0.860213

that small gaps can cause large changes (as much as 5 to 10 dB) in the reflectivity, especially at the lower frequencies. It was also shown that small gaps can cause variations in chamber performance, and these variations can have a detrimental effect on the ability of the chamber to meet its specification.

Acknowledgement – The authors would like to thank C. Devor of the Lehman Chambers Program of Paul Lehman, Inc., for supplying the absorber parameters and for supporting this work.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. Anzai, Y. Naito, T. Mizumoto, in *Proc. of the IEEE 1995 Intern. Symp. on Electromagnetic Compatibility*, Atlanta, GA, pp. 297-302.
- [2] K. Liu, in *Proc. of the IEEE 1996 Intern. Symp. on Electromagnetic Compatibility*, Santa Clara, CA, pp. 156-161.
- [3] R.T. Johnk, A.R. Ondrejka, H.W. Medley, *Natl. Inst. Stand. Technol., Tech. Note, to be published.*
- [4] R.T. Johnk and A. Ondrejka, in *Proc. of the IEEE 1997 Intern. Symp. on Electromagnetic Compatibility*, Austin, TX, pp. 537-542.
- [5] R.T. Johnk, A.R. Ondrejka, H.W. Medley, in *Proc. of the IEEE 1998 Intern. Symp. on Electromagnetic Compatibility*, Denver, CO, pp. 8-13.
- [6] R.T. Johnk, A.R. Ondrejka, C.L. Holloway, in *Proc. of the IEEE 1998 Intern. Symp. on Electromagnetic Compatibility*, Denver, CO, pp. 290-295.
- [7] C.L. Holloway, P. McKenna, and D.A. Steffen, in *Proc. of the IEEE 1997 Intern. Symp. on Electromagnetic Compatibility*, Austin, TX, pp. 60-65.
- [8] G. Mur, *IEEE Trans. Electromag. Compat.*, **39**(1), pp. 377-382, 1981.
- [9] C.L. Holloway, R.R. DeLyser, R.F. German, P. McKenna, and M. Kanda, *IEEE Trans. Electromag. Compat.*, **39**(1), pp. 33-47, 1997.
- [10] E.F. Kuester and C.L. Holloway, *IEEE Trans. Electromag. Compat.*, **36**(4), pp. 300-306, 1994.
- [11] E.F. Kuester and C.L. Holloway, *IEEE Trans. Microwave Theory Tech.*, **38**(11), pp. 1752-1755, 1990.
- [12] ANSI-C63.6, *American National Standards Institute, IEEE*, 1998.

Figure 1: Gaps in ferrite tiles mounted on a wall.

Figure 2: Time-domain measured backscatter coefficient for ferrite tiles with and without gaps.

Figure 3: The three dimensional ferrite tile with gap computational volume.

Figure 5: a) Ferrite tiles with gaps backed by dielectric layer and ground plane; b) effective layer model of ferrite tiles with gaps.

Figure 4: FDTD results of a ferrite tile dielectric absorber with various gap sizes. The ferrite tile had a width of 10 cm, a thickness of 6.5 mm, and the dielectric layer was 13 mm thick with $\epsilon_r = 2$.

Figure 6: Comparison of the effective layer model of the ferrite tile with gaps to results obtained from a FDTD model of the gaps.

Figure 7: Variations in the chamber performance as a function of gap sizes for a chamber of width 10.36 m, length 21.34 m, and height 8.23 m.

Figure 9: Variations in the chamber performance as a function of gap sizes for a chamber of width 11.58 m, length 19.81 m, and height 8.02 m.

Figure 8: Deviation from OATS as a function of gap sizes for a chamber of width 10.36 m, length 21.34 m, and height 8.23 m.

Figure 10: Deviation from OATS as a function of gap sizes for a chamber of width 11.58 m, length 19.81 m, and height 8.02 m.